

ANALYSIS OF FACTORS CONNECTING THE CONCEPTS OF LANGUAGE AND SOCIETY

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Annotation

Language contributes to the development of a society and society and its value is reflected in its language. That is, the interdependence of language and society is a topic of debate that involves a lot of content. There is a natural connection between the language spoken by members of a group living in a community and the uniqueness of that community. The aim of this scientific work is also to identify the means by which language and society are related and to illustrate them with examples.

Key words – social value, society, interdependence of language and society, identity, content, perspectives, ideologies, linguistic, non-linguistic, characteristic abilities, language acquisition, linguistic creativity.

INTRODUCTION

Language is not isolated entity; it is a main part of the society which uses it. It is “a system of signs that is seen as having itself a social value” (Kramsh, Language). At the same time society and its elements are reflected in its language. Language, in turn, contributes to the development of society. That is, it is a topic of discussion, which includes a great deal of content. Every position pronounced in a particular language contains socially specific meaning which can

be easily overlooked unless one is familiar with the society. “There is a natural connection between language spoken by members of social group and that group’s identity” (Ibid).

Much research has been done and many opinions have been expressed around the world about language and its features. We use language in society, we exist in society. Language serves as a carrier of information in this society. This is a scientific work: the study of the relationship between language and society, in the process of which the works and writings of some researchers and scholars were widely used, in particular: Ferdinand Saussure, Ibid, Kramsh, Chomskiy, Bannet, Ashurova, Galiyeva, and others.

The ability to use language is a mental ability, and mental ability is the result of brain activity, and it develops and coexists with society. In this sense, language always binds society. Language has not only meaning but also significance, and each speech is a great event that demonstrates an evaluative direction that reflects and evokes the perspectives, ideologies, and identities of specific social groups.

These questions can be discussed in the research:

- a) What are the peculiarities of language?
- b) In what ways is the connection between language and society manifested?
- c) What are the means of connecting language and society?

All the elements and tools that are important for revealing the relationship between language and society and the examples that prove them constitute the object of this research work.

BACKGROUND KNOWLEDGE

The field of linguistics, since Noam Chomsky’s revolutionary work in the 1960’s, has focused on explaining and identifying the unique features of human language, which are believed to consist of some a prior knowledge of the system

of language. Chomsky argued for this based on two primary distinctions between human language and other learned human behaviors. These two extraordinary features of human language were: language acquisition and linguistic creativity. On the first Chomsky said, “Knowledge of language arises on the basis of very scattered and inadequate data and that there are uniformities in what is learned that are in no way uniquely determined by the data itself” (Chomsky 1966).

On the second he said, “An essential property of language is that it provides the means for expressing indefinitely many thoughts and for reacting appropriately in an indefinite range of new situations” (Chomsky 1966). Essentially, human language is acquired regardless of varied and flawed input, and it endlessly adapts to new situations. These two properties of human language are most salient to Chomsky. He suggests that in order to display these puzzling abilities, humans possess a language organ “as real as the liver,” (Chomsky 2000). He claims that these unique abilities can only be attributed to a biologically unique structure. Recent work has suggested that many aspects of human language are not unique to humans. Sensory-motor ability in primates, dolphins and some birds displays similar phonetic ability to that of humans (Chomsky 2000). But parallels to Chomsky’s two characteristic abilities – language acquisition and linguistic creativity – are not clear in the animal kingdom. However, there may be a human non-linguistic parallel which sheds light on possible origins of these unique abilities.

METHODOLOGY

A. Research Design

Language performs various functions in the society and the society does the same way. If one will not exist, the other one will be affected. Language is the primary tool for communication purposes, for establishing peace and order in our society, for showing authority and power, and for attaining goals and objectives.

Language is both a system of communication between individuals and a social phenomenon. The area of language and society – sociolinguistics – is intended to show how our use of language is governed by such factors as class, gender, race, etc. Language is an important means of communication that draws people and nations together. Language is developed in society, lives in society and serves for the community. “Language is considered a main tool of communication and cognition” (Ashurova, Galiyeva2018). We address the language in any form of communication. For example: we use the language in greeting, message, writing, talking, receiving and searching, speaking, congratulating, participating in festivals, exchanging ideas etc. Also “language is a means of storing and transmitting information and different knowledge structures which are externalized in linguistic expressions” (Ashurova, Galiyeva2018). All the words in the language keep meaning and content, and enrich others with the same information.

B. Instruments

Language has social function; it helps people to establish maintain relationships. It means, language is principally used for communication processes , it is also used to establish and maintain social relationships. However the users of even the same language speak differently from each other. That kind of language each of them chooses to use in part determined by his social background. Term of relationships between language and society, it is an exploration of a bidirectional relationship between the language and its users. By the reaction of relationships between language and society, speech community is appeared and a speech community is a group of people who share a set of rules and norms for communication and interpretation of speech. A speech community includes everything from intonation, vocabulary, to body position and eye contact and a speech community is a group of people who share one or more varieties of

language and the rules for using those varieties in everyday communication. The idea of a speech community allows people to do two things:

- Focus on a smaller social unit than all the speakers of language;
- Get away from the idea that one language to one culture.

In other words, speech community is defined as a group of people who from a community and share the same language or particular variety of language.

The important characteristic of a speech community are people speak the same language; the members of group must interact linguistically with other members of communication; they may share similar attitudes toward linguistic norms.

Speech variety, also known as language variety, refers to any distinguishable form of speech used by a speaker or group of speakers. Distinctive characteristics of speech variety are mainly reflected in its pronunciation, syntaxes and vocabulary. Speech variety can be reason for communicative competence and a communicative competence is speaker's underlying knowledge of rules of grammar and rules for their use in socially appropriate circumstances, for example speaking formally or informally...

C. Data Collection and Analysis

Social knowledge is essential for membership in speech community. Social knowledge increase speech effectiveness.

Main factors of effective speaker's style include:

- Age of addressee;
- Social background of addressee;
- Relative status and solidarity between speaker and addressee
- Colloquial style: vernacular;
- Social dialect survey;
- Observer's paradox can be overcome by manipulating the topic of interview.

Another element of social language relatives is language shift, when communities who share a native language abandon it, and collectively shift to speaking another one. Language shift is always preceded by multilingualism and language shift can happen readily or slowly. Whenever two cultures, populations with different languages come in intense contact, shift is a possibility.

Social class is a controversial concept, no general agreement as to the exact nature or definition or existence of social classes. In social class linguistic variation can be seen. Linguistic variation can be analyzed in terms of social networks: the grouping of people based on the frequency and quality of interaction (figure 1). In this, network to help analysis how often the members of these groups are same and how often they are completely different.

Figure 1. Main components of relationship between language and society

RESULTS

Human social life classification displays these same traits of finding pattern and order out of inconsistent data and adapting to new situations by expanding the system seemingly infinitely. From these abilities of language features human

language differ than other languages with people' mind and and life in society. People live in society and communicate each other in society(see figure 2).

Figure 2. Society effects on language.

DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

Language is the reflection of a society with its all social values, norms, components and many other characteristics. Learning language without its social connection is a recipe for becoming a “fluent fool. A fluent fool is someone who speaks a foreign language, but does not understand the social or philosophical content of that language” (Bennett 1993). It means that language is inseparable phenomena which mirror a society. At the same time society and its value are reflected in its language. Language, in turn, contributes to the development of society. That is, it is a topic of discussion, which includes a great deal of content. Every position pronounced in a particular language contains specific meaning which can be easily overlooked unless one is familiar with the system of society. There is a natural connection between language spoken by members of social group and that group's identity.

As we know, the ability use of language is clearly a mental ability and thus, at least to modern sensibilities, one that is dependent on brain function. Mental ability is result of brain function and it is developed and lives with society. From this side, language always connects society. Language not only has meaning but also value, and every utterance exhibits an evaluative orientation, reflecting and

evoking the perspectives, ideologies, and identities of particular social groups.

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